

Community Leadership Engagement in Government Intervention Programmes on Poverty Alleviation and Sustainable Rural Development in Rivers State

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Abstract

The study investigated community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State. The study which adopted descriptive survey research design was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The population of the study comprised of all the traditional rulers and community development committee (CDC) members in the 23 L.G.A in Rivers State. A sample of 115 traditional rulers and 230 CDC members was drawn using stratified random sampling technique. A questionnaire titled: "Community Leadership Engagement in Government Intervention Programme Questionnaire (CLEGIPQ)" developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The instrument was properly validated and a reliability index of 0.84 was obtained through Cronbach Alpha method. Mean, mean set, standard deviation and rank order were used to test the hypotheses 0.05 level of significance. Results of the study revealed that factors hindering community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State include: inappropriate programme design; lack of effective collaboration and complementation among the three tiers of government; adoption of a top-to-bottom approach and lack of political will to address socio-economic issues. The study showed that the likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes include among others: facilitation of dialogue between government and stakeholders; transparency; effective decision making; and it helps in identifying the needs of the community and ensuring that programmes reflect their aspirations, perspectives and priorities. Based on the findings, conclusion was drawn and the following recommendations among others were made: government should adequately engage community leaders in the planning and implementation of intervention programmes and government should engage in dialogue with targeted beneficiaries of intervention programmes at the planning and implementation stages.

Keywords: Community development, community leadership, poverty alleviation, government intervention and community engagement

INTRODUCTION

Community development is a continuous thing that moves from one stage to another. Every community desires or aspires for improved provision of facilities or amenities that enhance the quality of human life. Sometimes the communities through their leaders request for things like good roads, hospitals/health centres, pipe-borne water, electricity, school etc to be built for their people to enhance sustainable community development which is part of the primary responsibility of the government. There is inequitable distribution of amenities and resources among the rural communities in Nigeria and Rivers State in particular. A visit to many rural communities across the thirty-six states in Nigeria shows that many rural communities are not accessible due deplorable roads; some do not have electricity; no internet network for communication, school are located far away, hospitals/health centres are not available no banks, no good markets, civic centres and no portable water for the people to drink.

Sometimes the members of the communities' resort to self-help in order to attend to their needs or solve some of their pressing problems. These efforts in some communities are commendable but they have not but they have not been adequate enough due to poverty and their inability to mobilise enough resources. Government is expected to use the public revenue generated through taxes and mineral resources to improve the lives of the citizens. Hence, they engage in various intervention programmes to enhance the socio-economic well-being of the people. Intervention programmes are those programmes or activities carried out by government that enhance the economic conditions of rural people by helping individuals and businesses to grow. Intervention programmes or activities of government boast socio-economic activities and help to bridge the gap between the rural and urban areas.

Over the years, government has initiated and implemented some programmes targeted towards poverty alleviation and the development of rural areas so that rural dwellers are not completely left out in the scheme of things. The low level of infrastructure and poor human capital development predominant in the rural areas have adverse effect on these intervention programmes. The situation is worsened by inadequate or sometimes total neglect of community leadership engagement in the planning and implementation of these programmes. Some of these programmes had faulty backgrounds, riddled with corruption and lack of political will to do what is right and follow programmes to logical conclusion. Sometimes these programmes end up enriching the political class with little or no benefit to the rural people (Okeke, 2008). In order to address the challenges of rural development, government have put several agencies in place to raise the standard of living of rural dwellers. However, studies have shown that most of these interventions are not working or have not yielded desired results because their impact is not felt in rural areas.

Community leaders are very important stakeholders in every intervention or development programmes meant for their communities. They are the leaders of their respective rural communities and they have influence over their people. They should be adequately engaged in the planning and implementation of intervention programmes meant for their people to enhance the effectiveness of such programmes. It appears they are over looked in most cases. It is against this background that the researcher decided to investigate community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

It is no longer news that so many Nigerians and Rivers people in particular are poor looking at the exchange rate, inflation rate insecurity and income level of many people in Rivers State, one imagines how these people are surviving and moving on. Government often claims that they are aware of the plight of the masses and formulate policies that will reduce the sufferings of the people and enhance their socio-economic well-being. The scourge of poverty and under development is more pronounced in the rural areas, where about 80% of the people are living below the poverty line of 1.90 dollars/ day, with dilapidated infrastructural facilities (Akinbode & Hazmat, 2017).

It has been observed that the impact of government policies and intervention programmes in addressing the level of poverty and under development in rural areas is very poor. Most agencies involved in the implementation of these policies and programmes lack accountability, transparency and the willingness to carry the rural dwellers along especially the community leaders. It is based on this premise that the researcher was motivated to investigate the engagement of community leaders in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

Ai and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. identify factors militating against community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.
2. ascertain the likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. What are the factors militating against community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State?
2. What are the likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of traditional rulers and community development committee (CDC) members on the factors militating against community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of traditional rulers and community development committee (CDC) members on the likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

Theoretical and Conceptual Literature Review

This study is anchored on the power theory. The power theory according to Luke in Hussaini (2014) proposes that the composition of leaders who regulate the affairs and the resources of a state are the ones exposing the poor into hardship. The dominant ruling class design unnecessary programmes without due consultations of the target beneficiaries and unreasonably mismanage the state or public resources. They in addition are the ones who decide on the allocation of wealth, job creation, general opportunities and revenue of the state. This attitude leads to the misuse of state resources by the few in power and the majority of the masses or citizens have little or no access to their basic social needs. Hence, the people are subjected to poverty on the basis of weak economy, political and social programmes imposed on them by the power holders.

This theory is relevant to this study especially the poverty situation in Rivers State which is attributed to poor governance and leadership. The state has abundant human and material resources capable of transforming the state out of the poverty trap. In the light of this situation poverty in Rivers State is seen as a leadership problem which is related to economic exploitation, poor governance and political marginalization. These are part of the factors responsible for poverty experienced in the state.

Conceptual Literature Review

Government intervention is the intentional interference of government in a countries economic system through regulatory actions or government deliberate actions to influence resource allocation and market mechanisms (Anger, 2000; Gberevbie, 2007). Examples of these interventions include taxes, subsidies, price control regulations, minimum wage legislation etc. Intervention programmes play significant roles in rural development and poverty alleviation. It promotes socio-economic development in the society (World Bank, 2001). It is a strategic policy framework designed to facilitate the transformation of peoples' behaviours, feelings and thoughts ranging from local and international levels geared towards uplifting the living standard of people in terms of education, health, agriculture, business and technological development (Arogundade, Adebisi & Ogunro, 2011).

The main focus of intervention programs irrespective of the policy agenda according to Cline-Cole and Maconache (2016) is to enhance individual values, attitude, knowledge and skills, improve socio-economic and infrastructural support and in general create a conducive environment for people to live and transact their businesses. Nigerian government have at various intervals pronounced and implemented various poverty alleviation and rural development programmes to address unemployment, poverty, under development and to promote opportunities to enhance productive ability of rural people and their socio-economic conditions (Hamilton, 2012). Examples of these programmes include: National Poverty Eradication Programme (NPE), Directorate for food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI), National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS) and many others. Many of these intervention programmes failed to achieve their objectives irrespective of the huge resources committed into them by the government. According to Obadan (2001) some of the factors which contributed to the failure of these poverty alleviation programmes include:

1. Lack of targeting mechanisms for the poor and the fact that most of the programmes do not focus directly on the poor.
2. Political and policy instability which have resulted to frequent policy changes and inconsistent implementation
3. Inadequate coordination of various programmes which have resulted to various institutions carrying out their own activities with resultant duplication of efforts and inefficient utilization of resources. Over lapping functions leads to institutional rivalry and conflicts.
4. Severe budgetary, management and governance problems.
5. Lack of accountability and transparency which make most of the programmes to serve as conduct pipes for draining national resources.
6. Inappropriate programmes design reflecting lack of the involvement of the beneficiaries in the formulation implementation of programmes.
7. Absence of target setting for ministries, agencies and programmes.
8. Absence of effective collaboration and complementation among the three levels of governments.
9. Most of the programmes lack mechanisms for their sustainability.

10. Over extended scope of activities of most institutions, which results to resources being spread too thinly on too many activities.

Obdan in Aminu and Onimisi (2014) argued that all efforts at poverty alleviation in Nigeria were essentially adhoc until the inauguration of poverty alleviation programme development by the government in 1994. Such programmes were not integrated into the overall development objectives and the management of these programmes were worsened by the adoption of a top to bottom approach in the implementation of the policies. The target groups who worsened by the adoption of a top to bottom approach in the implementation of the policies. The target groups who are the poor in the society living predominantly in the rural areas, were hardly reached, their leadership were hardly involved due to the fact the programmes existed at the state and local government headquarters. They failed to have adequate linkage with the traditional rulers and community leaders for effective penetration of the grass roots (Eze, 2003; Yakubu and Aderonmu, 2010). This gap lead to the inauguration of National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (LEEDS) at the state and local government levels. This policy aimed at adopting a wholistic approaching in tackling wide range of socio-economic and political issues facing the country, especially the rural areas.

We had the seven point agenda by the administration of President Yar' Adua and the transformation agenda of the President Goodluck Jonathan's administration which were aimed at correcting the flaws in the country's efforts for development and sustainable growth. Lack of continuity, consistency and commitment according to Usigbe (2011) resulted to rising unemployment, inequality and poverty, which indicates the failure of these policies. The immediate past administration of President Mohammadu Buhari embarked on cash transfers pf N5000 (five thousand naira) to the poorest people in the country. Up till date, the people that receive this money are yet to be verified. How can N 5, 000/ month alleviate someone from poverty in the current economic hardship in the country? It is therefore clear that Nigerian government lacks the political will to address socio-economic issues in Nigeria (Aminu and Ominisi, 2014).

Ovwasa and Onimisi (2021) pointed out that social exclusion in the form of lack of social connectedness, cohesion, and inclusion of community members have direct relationship to social and physical development, have direct relationship to social and physical development, which can invariably encourage civic participation in the overall community development project. Exclusion has remained the biggest challenge of community development in Nigeria. Community development is more meaningful when the people actively participate as agents and not just passive beneficiaries because the people themselves should monitor the developmental projects in their local communities. The social exclusion of the community members in the conception, design and implementation of many community development projects have led to failure of such projects (Odo, 2012). These people suffering exclusion in day-to-day activities in their communities because of neglects tend to become depressed, feel discontented and aggressive. This makes a lot of them to engage in criminal and violent activities, they will begin to distrust the society, hence guns and ammunitions become operational tools in their hands. This serves as a constraint to any community development programme in these communities (Adah and Abasihim, 2015).

One other major factor that have contributed to the failure of rural development programmes to achieve their goals of poverty eradication and sustainable development in Nigeria today is the problem of purposeful, critical and knowledgeable leadership. Leadership failure has become very pervasive in Nigeria, permeating every facet of our national life. According to Oruonye (2013), the following factors have contributed to leadership failure in Nigeria:

1. Lack of rule of law and non-adherence to constitutionality;
2. absence of development oriented leadership;
3. Absence of accountability and transparency;
4. Corruption;
5. Electoral malpractices;
6. Craziiness for riches, wealth, power, selfish interest etc.

It is therefore necessary to engage community members and their leadership in programmes aimed at bringing transformation and sustainable development. According to www.socialpinpoint.com, community engagement can transform communities. By encouraging public participation in projects that impact society, it facilitates fair, equitable and sustainable outcomes. The following are six reasons why an effective community engagement strategy is important:

1. Community engagement facilitates dialogue between the decision-makers and the stakeholders. By engaging in a community led dialogue, decision-makers (government) will understand what the people like or dislike about their community and the initiatives that could impact it. This helps government to get a better understanding of the community's needs and aspirations.

2. Diverse perspective empower decision-making as inputs on community initiatives needs to be gathered from a diverse representative group in the community. When engagement projects are inundated with input from those with the loudest voices or strongest opinion, the outcomes are only beneficial to one group and can be detrimental to the community as a whole. Without allowing a diverse set of perspectives to be aired, government can be swayed by the loudest voices and put their focus in the wrong areas. The government should seek out overlooked or marginalized voices and create avenues for people of all backgrounds, motivations and persuasions to speak up. This will give a balanced understanding of the community's views and enhance the value of the final decision by government.
3. Engagement of community leaders and their citizens will transparency: Community leadership engagement is a public process, and it keeps decision-makers accountable. The community deserves to have transparency over decision-making process and should feel that input was taken into account. It equally gives individuals in the community opportunities to understand how a perspective or need that was different from their own had to be catered for and give them a better understanding and acceptance of a final decision or outcome. By engaging all stakeholders of public policy projects will strengthen democracy and ensure that people have a say over the decisions that impact their day- to – day lives.
4. It creates greater sense of community ownership: The community members have a deep and intimate knowledge of their local area, as well as scientific, technical, historical, and cultural insights. When these perspectives are shared between all parties and applied into decision-making, public decision-makers will be better informed, more confident, and able to meet all needs.
5. Community engagement helps initiatives to run smoothly: Community engagement can help to identify roadblocks, which might increase costs of projects in terms of time and money. By taking an on-going scan of the community's needs, priorities, and key stakeholders, you can ensure that the project runs smoothly and that the budget is used effectively. Complaints and protests that might otherwise hold up your initiative can be identified, addressed and catered for when your strategy, resources and budget are established.
6. Create some fun: Online community engagement and public participation can create so much fun. You will have the opportunity to fuel big dreams, talk about community aspirations, and brainstorm with your neighbours.

According to www.linkedin.com community engagement can enhance the measurement of health and well-being of people in several ways. It can help to identify the needs, preferences and values of the community and ensure that the measurement reflects their perspectives and priorities. It is equally beneficial because it will increase the validity, reliability and accuracy of the data by involving community members in designing, collecting, and analyzing the information. Engaging the community in interpreting and applying the findings. And, it can foster the development of skills, knowledge and capacities of the community, as well as the researchers and practitioners involved in the measurement.

METHODOLOGY

This study made use of descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised of all the traditional rulers and community development committee (CDC) members in the twenty-three (23) Local Government Areas (LGA's) in Rivers State. A sample of three hundred and forty-five (345) respondents comprising of one hundred and fifteen (115) traditional rulers and two hundred and thirty (230) CDC members was drawn through stratified random sampling technique from the twenty-three (23) LGA's in Rivers State. Five (5) traditional rulers and ten (10) CDC members were selected from each of the LGA's in Rivers State. A questionnaire entitled, "Community Leadership Engagement in Government Intervention Programmes Questionnaire (CLEGIPQ)" developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The questionnaire instrument was structured on a four-point rating Likert Scale. The instrument which had fourteen (14) items was subjected to face and content validity, and a reliability index of 0.84 was obtained through Cronbach Alpha method. Mean, mean set, standard deviation and rank order were used to analyse the research questions, while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. A total of 345 copies of questionnaire were administered to the respondents and 330 copies were retrieved.

RESULTS

Research Questionnaire One: What are the factors militating against community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean scores, standard deviation, mean set and rank order analysis of the responses of traditional rulers and CDC members on the factors militating against community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

S/N	Factors Militating Against Community Leadership Engagement in Government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development	Traditional rulers N = 115		CDC members N = 230		Mean sets	Rank order	Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂			
1.	Inappropriate programme design.	3.08	0.69	3.24	0.65	3.16	7 th	Agree
2.	Lack of effective collaboration and complementation among the three levels of government.	3.42	0.59	3.46	0.56	3/44	1 st	Agree
3.	Adoption of atop-to-bottom approach.	3.36	0.63	3.44	0.57	3.40	3 rd	Agree
4.	Adhoc approach nature of most intervention and sustainable rural development programmes.	3.30	0.65	3.26	0.63	3.28	6 th	Agree
5.	Lack of continuity, consistency and commitment	3.28	0.66	3.32	0.62	3.30	5 th	Agree
6.	Lack of political will to address socio-economic issues in Rivers State	3.40	0.60	3.42	0.58	3.41	2 nd	Agree
7.	Inability of the people to hold government accountable for the failure of intervention and sustainable rural development	3.38	0.62	3.40	0.60	3.39	4 th	Agree
Aggregate mean and standard deviation.		3.32	0.63	3.36	0.60			

Criterion mean = 2.50

Table 1 shows that all the items had mean scores that were greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. They were accepted by the respondents as the factors hindering community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes in poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development. The items in the rank order of 1st to 7th showed that item number 2 with a mean set score of 3.44 ranked 1st while item number 1 with mean set score of 3.16 ranked 7th. The aggregate mean score of 3.32 for the traditional rulers and 3.36 for the CDC members which were above the criterion mean and closely related indicate that the respondents shared common opinion on the factors militating against community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

Therefore, the factors hindering community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State include: inappropriate programme design; lack of effective collaboration and complementation among the three tiers of government; adoption of a top-to-bottom approach; adhoc approach nature of government intervention programmes; lack of continuity, consistency and commitment; lack of political will to address socio-economic issues in Rivers State; and inability of the people to hold government accountable for the failure of intervention and sustainable rural development programme.

Research Question Two: What are the likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean scores, standard deviation, mean set and rank order analysis of the responses of traditional rulers and CDC members on the likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

S/N	Likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programme on Poverty Alleviation And Sustainable Rural Development in Rivers State	Traditional rulers N = 115		CDC members N = 230		Mean sets	Rank order	Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂			
1.	Facilitation of dialogue between government and stakeholders or targeted beneficiaries.	3.52	0.56	3.54	0.55	3.53	2 nd	Agree
2.	Effective decision making	3.46	0.61	3.48	0.58	3/47	5 th	Agree
3.	Engagement of community leaders will enhance transparency.	3.48	0.59	3.52	0.56	3.50	3 rd	Agree
4.	It gives the community members deep sense of belonging and ownership of the programme	3.54	0.54	3.58	0.52	3.56	1 st	Agree
5.	Community leadership engagement will help the programme to run smoothly by identifying and tackling some factors which might delay the programme and increase its cost.	3.44	0.63	3.42	0.62	3.43	6 th	Agree
6.	It will help to identify the needs of the community and ensure that programmes reflect their aspirations, perspectives and priorities.	3.50	0.57	3.46	0.60	3.48	4 th	Agree
7.	Engagement of community leaders in planning and implementation of government intervention programmes will inflate the cost.	2.32	0.65	2.28	0.66	2.30	7 th	Disagree
Aggregate mean and standard deviation.		3.32	0.59	3.33	0.58			

Criterion Mean = 2.50

Table 2 shows that items number 1 to 6 had mean scores that were greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. they were accepted by the respondents as the likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programme on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State. Item number 7 had mean score that was less than the criterion mean hence it was rejected. The items in the rank order of 1st to 7th showed that item number 4 with mean set score of 3.56 ranked 1st, while item number 7 with mean set score of 2.30 ranked 7th. The aggregate mean score of 3.32 for the traditional rulers and 3.33 for the CDC members which were above the criterion mean, and closely related each other, showed that the respondents unanimously agreed on the likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programme on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development.

Therefore, the likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State include: facilitation of dialogue between government and stakeholders or targeted beneficiaries; effective decision making; transparency; deep sense of belonging and ownership of programmes; helps programmes to run smoothly; and it helps to identify the needs of the community and ensure that programmes reflect their aspirations, perspectives and priorities.

Test of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of traditional rulers and CDC members on the factors militating against community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

Table 3: z-test of difference between the mean scores of traditional rulers and CDC members on the factors militating against community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

Status	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of sign.	Decision
Traditional ruler	115	3.32	0.63	343	0.564	± 1.960	0.05	Ho ₁ Not Significant
CDC members	230	3.36	0.60					

Results in table 3 indicated that the mean scores of traditional rulers and CDC members stood at 3.32 and 3.36 respectively, these mean scores appear closely related. Furthermore, at 343 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance the calculated z-score of 0.564 was by far less than the z-critical or table value of ± 1.960 . The researcher therefore failed to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, it was established that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of traditional rulers and CDC members on the factors militating against community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of traditional rulers and CDC members on the likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

Table 4: z-test of difference between the mean scores of traditional rulers and CDC members on the likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

Status	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of sign.	Decision
Traditional ruler	115	3.32	0.59	343	0.149	± 1.960	0.05	Ho ₂ Not Significant
CDC members	230	3.33	0.58					

Results in table 4 showed that the mean scores of traditional rulers and CDC members stood at 3.32 and 3.33 respectively. These mean scores look closely related. Furthermore, at 343 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance, the calculated z-value of 0.149 was by far less than the z-critical or table value of ± 1.960 . the researcher therefore failed to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, the researcher established that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of traditional rulers and CDC members on the likely benefits of community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

Results of the study have revealed the factors hindering community leadership engagement in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development to include inappropriate programme design; lack of effective collaboration and complementation among the various tiers of government; adoption of a top-to-bottom approach; adhoc approach nature of the programmes; lack of continuity, consistency and commitment; lack of political will to address socio-economic issues and inability of the people to hold government accountable for failure of intervention and sustainable rural development programmes. Most of the government intervention programmes are conceived and designed at Abuja by federal government and these programmes are adopted by the state governments. The various communities and citizens that the programmes are meant for are not involved or interacted with to enable them make their inputs in designing the programmes. This results to programme designs that does not reflect the wishes and desires of the people, hence such programmes are most likely to fail.

There is supposed to be effective collaboration and complementation among the three tiers government in terms of decision making and implementation of programmes aimed at improving the welfare and socio-economic status of the people in rural communities. The people in the rural communities are mostly peasant farmers who are poor. These people are better known by their various local government authorities. It is unfortunate that the 774 LGA in Nigeria are only existing but not functioning. They have been made irrelevant by state governments, hence LG.A authorities are almost figure heads without portfolios. They are marginalized and hardly carried along by the state and federal governments in decision making and planning of intervention programmes affecting the poor and rural communities.

This scenario hinders the engagement of the community leaders and the success of the programmes. Related to this is the top-to-bottom approach of decision making which makes the integration of the targeted beneficiaries in the planning and implementation of intervention programmes difficult (Aminu & Onimisi, 2014).

There is lack of adequate sensitization and enlightenment of people on the planned intervention programmes before their implementation. Government often uses adhoc and fire bridge approach in the planning and implementation of such programmes hence they fail to have adequate linkage with traditional rulers and CDC members for better penetration of the grassroots. The existence of this gap according to Odo (2012) causes discontentment, depression and aggressiveness among the people. Also, lack of continuity, consistency and commitment to address the socio-economic issues and under development of rural communities is a serious factor hindering the engagement of community leaders in the planning and implementation of intervention programmes in Rivers State. The government is not transparent, it does not want the community people to know much about the cost of such programmes. They hide so many things from the public. Lack of continuity in governance as a result of tenure issues and politicisation of government programmes results to inconsistencies in the planning and implementation of government programmes. All these factors constitute part of the lack of political will on the side of government to do the right thing in terms of addressing the challenges of poor people in Nigeria (Aminu & Onimisi, 2014).

The study also revealed the likely benefits of the engagement of community leaders in government intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State as: facilitation of dialogue; effective decision making; transparency; sense of ownership of programmes; helps programmes to run smoothly; and it helps in identifying the needs of the people. The engagement of the community leaders and their people on issues concerning them is very necessary. This will promote a lot of goodwill relationship between the stakeholders and the government. It will give them a sense of recognition and partnership with the government for the progress and development of their people.

Integrating the community leadership in the planning and implementation of government intervention programmes will help government to understand what the people actually wants. It will help them to make their inputs in the programme, hence it will help them to see the programme as their own. Supporting this view Obadan (2001) states that it will enhance the trust and transparency of government before the people. This will promote the success of intervention programmes because it will help such programmes to run smoothly in order to achieve desired results.

CONCLUSION

Government over the years have formulated so many good intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development. It is unfortunate to state that almost all of these programs failed in their mandates due to the exclusion of the targeted beneficiaries or stakeholders in the planning and implementation of such programs as well as lack of political will, sincerity and commitment to the success of these programmes by the government. It is therefore concluded by the researcher that without adequate engagement of the community leaders (stakeholders) and demonstration of enough political will and commitment to the success of the intervention programmes, such programmes may continue not to yield the desired results.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings:

1. Government should adequately engage community leaders in the planning and implementation of intervention programmes on poverty alleviation and sustainable rural development in Rivers State.
2. Government should engage in dialogue with the stakeholders or targeted beneficiaries of intervention programmes to ensure that programmes meet the needs and aspirations of the people.
3. Government should show enough political will to address the socio-economic challenges facing the people of Rivers State rather than engaging on political rhetories and favouring one zone at the expense of others.

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